

A Study: The Future of the Internet of Things and its Home Applications

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Abstract-Internet of Things (IoT) is a network of human Meshing with everything that exists around us like our daily life communication through mobiles or the internet. In the next two or three years of (2020), the internet will be changed to IoT. IoT can connect the smart objects through different technologies like Bluetooth, ZigBee, and Radio Frequency Identifier (RFID). This paper highlights the effects of IoT on human beings and their privacy, we suggest how to use IoT with smart home technology to improve the living style. Smart home technology provides automated, intelligent, smart, innovative and ubiquitous services to residential users through Information Communication Technology (ICT). The IoT usage has some drawbacks like fraud and looting people, as a human being will be a part of the IoT. We also discuss practical examples of a point-to-point connection between the devices. In IoT enabled smart home environment various things such as lighting, home applications, connecting computers, security camera, linking home with Civil Defense.[1, 2]

Keywords: IoT Future, Smart Home, Next Generation, Implicit Messages, Smart Object.

I. INTRODUCTION

IoT is a new concept that connects everything to control the physical environment. The type of control can be through monitoring, observing, processing, and analyzing data that can be generated by sensor devices, intelligent objects, or reboots [1]. The development of computer networks led to the transition to a new stage, through which networks can be connected more than one device. Mobile phones have grown exponentially and many applications have been built on phones, to making phones smart, like smart TVs, smartwatch, and smart pouch. Hence, these smart inventions were imposed on the user, and there is a high demand to connect these things with each other through a single network. This network can identify everything using new IP Address (IPv6). With this acceleration in technology, we are able to create a smart home. Where we have a suitable environment to occupy everything that is intelligent inside the house.[2, 3]

The idea of a smart home began with the control of energy and electricity, which are the main elements of the individual's expenses. Then came the smart gadgets at home, not only these gadgets on electricity, but entered the cooking, mirror, and even with a cup of coffee[4]. IoT can make human life more enjoyable and comfortable compared to the past. Using the Smart Home, we can control and monitor the associated applications in its range. The most common applications can be lighting, heating, temperature, windows, doors, and curtains. Some home applications can be linked to mobile devices. A smart life helps people to reduce their efforts, time, and cost. A smart home also referred to as connected home or e-Home is an environment for living [2], that has a highly advanced automatic system. A smart home appears "intelligent" because its daily activities are monitored by a computer. A smart home consists of many technologies via home networking for improving quality of living. A smart home is a place that has highly advanced automatic systems for controlling and monitoring lighting and

temperature, home appliances, multimedia equipment, and security systems, and many other functions. IoT plays an important role in building a smart home. Through IoT almost every object of our daily life in a home can be connected to the internet. IoT allows monitoring and controlling all of these connected objects regardless of time and location.[3]

In this research, we consider two main issues. Firstly, we will collect information about tools and things. We will try to find a way how to link all these accessories to each other using IP addresses. Secondly, we will talk about the impact of this technology on human using for a long time. In conclusion, we will present a law that will be able to control the fair use of this development and progress in society. There must be legislation and laws so that people can be reassured whenever they are in need. The set of laws and regulations should be added when needed and when there is confusion or misunderstanding of the method of use.

This paper was organized as follows. In section II, we describe the existing research work. In section III, we describe the outgoing and future work. In section IV, we provide a conclusion and recommendations.

II. The existing research work

It is analyzed that still, people are exploring the IoT? Some people using smart tools without knowing that tools can be a part of the IoT as shown in (Fig 1). Since many existing home automation systems use Bluetooth or ZigBee for wireless connection. WiFi is also an alternate solution with the introduction of IPv6 that can connect of large number of embedded devices and its ubiquitous presence in many CE devices. The security challenges in IoT include privacy, authentication, and secure end-to-end connection. In addition, with the presence of multiple smart home standards currently used in the market a security scheme is needed to consider inter-compatibility among the multiple standards. It has become apparent that Personal Area Network (PAN) or personal wireless communication devices have become proxies for many people as well as inanimate objects.[5] One of the first Bluetooth scanners developed was used by small group of participants to record contacts and contact durations between the group members. The basic idea was to scan for near-range Bluetooth device using a probe device and then to use this type of data in simulation models for contact based infectious disease spread.[6]

there is something wrong with this video, and they said we feel uncomfortable, "I'm not happy". After a day, were reversed video was unlike the students, so I took the first set second video and took the second set the first video. I asked them viewing. The first video shows the effect on the group, which said the bad video, they said that we feel satisfaction, while the second group was rested after paving the second video, that there is nothing wrong in this video, we said we do not feel satisfaction said. So what is the reason? What is the secret? that videos are the same thing, but I put including, audio track which is very small, hardly heard, because the higher the sound of rain, almost overshadowing it, I've had audio track first is a voice recording, to a person, sends positive messages: you are great person, you're a person impressive, you will succeed in your life, and continued to give, and so the stimulus and encouragement and positive messages, even improve a person's actions and promote it. [17, 18]

Figure 1: IoT tools

The section below describes how we can use IoT tools in our daily life. There are a lot of cattle farms around the world. To monitor the health status and fertility the percentage of certain hormones in the body, which indicates the best time for milking. Which helps in making accurate decisions to improve the production process. Teeth brush is also an example of IoT, to take decision how long we should clean our teeth in the morning. The IoT can help us dental coverage, proper use, and gives statistics on oral health[2]. Thread example, the Mirror will be changed, and connect to the Internet. So, before you go out of the house, then stop, and you will know the weather, the latest news, information on the condition of the road, and can find out the latest tweets, as well as to check my email. Cup philosopher was known as the drink, in the sense that he knows the type of beverage that contains it, and gives statistics at the end of the day about unhealthy drinks. An intelligent air conditioner can be connected to the Internet. There will be no need to call people to turn on the air conditioner, and be cool or warm the room, upon arrival, but and through mobile, is to use an application, to control the temperature.[7]

A remote control is also an example of IoT, when you leave the house for some time, and go on vacation, or traveling outside the country. There would be no need to notify neighbors or relatives, or even hire a guard, to monitor the house and watered the plants with water. It is a network of surveillance cameras building, which is connected to the Internet and using an application from the mobile phone. You are seeing the house and follow-up plants, move the camera, and even lighting the house, or even a fire alarm, and can we water the planting. Egg dish in the refrigerator connected to the Internet. When shopping for an egg dish, we need to know how many eggs in the refrigerator, and how many pills corrupt.[8] This provided us a smart refrigerator and connected to the internet. Parent device compassionate, at the entrance of the house, gives the mother a compassionate, a summary of the family. When children returned from school, from whom he cleaned his teeth, did you eat my mother's medicines on time? This machine can attend a cup of coffee or tea for drinking after waking up from a siesta. A sports shirt, after a rest, can wear a sports shirt, a provider of sensors. Working on the sports performance analysis, and the health of the heart, breathing, accurately, and send it through a special application on mobile jerseys. Cooking pot, a cooking pot connected to the Internet, it is suggested recipes from cuisines and determines the proper amount of each dish you want to prepare.[9]

Figure 2: The privet connection for one person

Extra containers connected to the Internet, when you return home, tells us mobile. The home container is full, and you emptied before entering the house, and spend an evening with the family. Fork connected to the Internet. These e-fork sets, how many calories are in the food you eat? The way of eating, you are slow or fast, and give the statistics at the end of the day. The number of dishes that have been dealt with, and is it healthy or not . Door smart lock, when you're ready to sleep, is the use of mobile. To shut down all external doors, equipped with a lock-mail and connected to the Internet, allowing select times of the lock, and conquest, automatically. The alarm in case the door was opened by someone in my absence. Smart bike, when touring bike connected to the Internet, you will tell the driver in the available trends. Why best way to avoid obstacles and traffic congestion and the human. Suitcases Smart, which shows not steal. Microsoft Corporation is working in cooperation with Samsonite to develop suitcases smart company, is expected to be available for purchase, and equipped with GPS. So, that the bags are working to send alerts to users of devices for protection from theft, or stay away from them. Samsung Corporation is working to develop this bag, so keep track of the traveler at the airport wherever he went.[7, 9-13]

III. The future of the Internet of Things

A man in nature needs someone, who cooperates with him and understands his ideas or inner feelings. In addition, the nature of life tends to isolate the person and his need to be alone with himself. All this is the result of life's stress and difficult requirements. From here, we expect the surrounding instruments to become in this person, which simulates his inner feelings, and thoughts. In this section we present our vision for this near future. When a person returns home after jogging he is exhausted, an automated refrigerator should measure the sweat and the water needed by the person. The TV should receive signals through the heartbeat, high blood sugar, and blood pressure. The TV should suggest a program according to the mood of a person. Then it should introduce landscaped with quiet and attractive music by its feeling. It tickles feelings, and stir conscience, we feel now that the evolution of human needs and wants to reach him, but it has a very serious aspect.[1, 14]

These devices that surround us and the elements of the surrounding environment will know about the rights of this vast amount of information. Clarification: through a simple signal sent from a small simple device that does not exceed the size of a grain of a (rice), this device is called Radio Frequency Identification (RFID). It is scientific research so far, so the stitches or the cultivation of a grain of rice RFID in the man's arm and through the sorting takes captures all the information about the human body and sends it to the extensions devises surrounding. Like the rest of the surrounding stuff around it, interact with it and interact with him. Unfortunately, this first step in looting humanitarian from us, so we are

going to be a thing. Privacy has become a serious issue in the online world, and the meaning of human privacy, so there is no longer something private, there is no longer anything to hide, and everyone knows everything about others.[15]

Apply the concept of Artificial Intelligence (AI), a deadly weapon is very dangerous, such as when they are giving awareness or intelligence even smarter and beyond the capabilities of the human sensory and analytical device, the subject in which so dangerous, how that was given to the network. Why all of this warning from artificial intelligence? Because it will simply become the mobile phones become smarter than humans. If we asked ourselves: what is the last thing you saved? The answer is my PIN number, what is the last number you saved, telephone number, or Student ID to someone who graduated from ten or twenty years. Why do not we keep the numbers we've become, and what happened to our minds. The reason said the phone has become smart than the man, we record all phone numbers and record all appointments in it, and anything in human memory needs it. And it disrupted the research capacity of the tool in the human skull. This tool is a giant force, dwarfed and dwarfed and become very lazy, and no longer remember Ditto because it relied on the Mobile phone. [16]

A German philosopher Old named Martin Heidegger 1889-1976 that person lived the horrors of the world wars I and II, and by what he saw of the destruction and the killing and technological development caused by the arms, back to the public and began to warn people that the technological development in the lives of human beings should legalize it completely technology advisement. He became advocates for the first time in life since that time the existence or the development or writing the Constitution governs the relationship of man with technological development. Is there a constitution in this way now, the answer is no. If we opened the United Nations Web site and villages, and we extracted the full list of human rights, we find that it consists of more than 30 articles, all of these articles there is no right to speak directly about the relationship of man with technological development, or even technology itself is almost mentioned.

Apply signals, or implicit messages, subliminal messages, will be spelled by example. There is a study on two groups of students (soldiers & officers), after obtaining the approval of them, because of this study manipulator of their feelings. They have been offered two syllables Video exactly the same thing, which is a scene rain down from the sky. These two videos a replica from the same source, but saved them something inside them, so that the first group that I watched the first video, and after watching it, he was asked: How do you feel? The answer: they feel happy "we feel fine", as the beautiful landscape, and feel quite comfortable, even though his time does not exceed 30 seconds. The second group of students who watched the same video for a period of 30 seconds, all that they said,

The second video: was contain audio track recorded messages are very negative, you're bad, you're nasty, I wonder when you spoke to your mother and Reassure her, do you think that you will succeed. Their cruelty and was recorded in the second video speech. The question, as long as they did not hear it, how it has affected them? There are sensors in the human body, we specialize in picking waves Thus, even if I did not hear the ear, the eye and did not see them. Small signals picked up by sensors in the human body, called subliminal signals or implicit signals. Here the mind remembers, conspiracy that took place in 2001, where the US military began to deal with the number of two million Arab Iraqi, where they was recording tapes and CDs containing Quranic recordings, religious lectures,

but these lectures, readings Quranic, they contain implicit messages, in the background, behind, and began to spread in all the cities of Iraq, this was the message, is: do not resist, throw your weapon, do not resist, you're weak, you cannot resist, you're weak.[19]

IV. The next generation challenges

The demand for energy will continuously increase. Current power grids were built decades ago, and despite the fact that they are regularly upgraded, The result of this current state is the transition of the traditional centralized grid towards a distributed hybrid energy generation system that heavily relies on renewable energy sources, such as wind and solar systems. Smart grid is a concept that integrates information and communication technologies (ICT) with grid power systems, in order to achieve efficient and intelligent energy generation and consumption. If demand is greater than the total generation, these systems could prevent the grid failure or major blackouts, and increase the reliability, quality, security and safety of the power grid. Smart grid solutions can be applied in every part of the grid: production, transmission and distribution. Recently, a fourth part of the smart grid, i.e. the smart home has become a major (mainstream) research and application interest in smart grid.[20, 21]

The Internet of Things (IoT) paradigm is based on intelligent and self configuring nodes (things) interconnected in a dynamic and global network infrastructure. It represents one of the most disruptive technologies, enabling ubiquitous and pervasive computing scenarios. IoT is generally characterized by real world and small things with limited storage and processing capacity, and consequential issues regarding reliability, performance, security, and privacy. On the other hand, Cloud computing has virtually unlimited capabilities in terms of storage and processing power, is a much more mature technology, and has most of the IoT issues at least partially solved. Thus, a novel IT paradigm in which Cloud and IoT are two complementary technologies merged together is expected to disrupt both current and future Internet. We call this new paradigm CloudIoT.[5, 22]

V. Conclusion

Security and convenience are two major requirements for successful deployment of IoT in a smart home. This paper proposes and implements a smart home system based on the Wi-Fi network. And summarizes the available standards in the network which are the building blocks of the home network and innovation. From United Nations charter, we extracted the full list of human rights, I found that there is no right about the relationship of a human with technological, or even technology itself is almost mentioned, finally, there is human privacy by using IoT.

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